

Eurocode 4 assessment for the sectional capacity of Circular Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes columns: High Strength Materials and local buckling effects considered.

D. Hernández-Figueirido^{*,a}, A. Piquer^a

^a Department of Mechanical Engineering and Construction, Universitat Jaume I, Castellón, Spain
hernandd@uji.es, ana.piquer@uji.es

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a study, based on experimental results, for the sectional capacity of Concrete-Filled Steel Tubes (CFST). A total of 670 experimental test of axially loaded Circular CFST stub columns published in the literature was summarized. The current design code in Europe, for composite columns, Eurocode 4, is considered in this study and its applicability for predicting the squash load of Circular CFST was examined using the experimental data. Database includes columns with high strength materials and thin-walled sections, which are also compared with current design code, despite they are not included in their field of application.

Keywords: concrete-filled steel tubes, high strength materials, local buckling, thin walled

1 INTRODUCTION

Concrete-Filled Steel Tubular (CFST) columns offer numerous advantages, including high strength, ductility, and enhanced fire resistance, making them increasingly popular in various structures [1] They outperform equivalent steel or reinforced concrete columns due to the steel tube providing permanent formwork and support during construction, reducing costs and time. Challenges such as brittle behaviour in high-strength concrete and local buckling in thin-walled steel tubes are addressed effectively in CFST columns. However, their full potential is hindered by limited understanding and absence of design codes for high-strength materials. This study evaluates existing European code, Eurocode 4[2], provision for CFST columns, considering high-strength materials and thin-walled sections.

Concrete-filled sections, comprised of concrete and steel, exhibit varied behaviour influenced by factors such as shape, column length, materials used, and the sectional aspect ratio. For concentrically axially loaded columns, their behaviour varies based on slenderness. Short columns with a small length-to-diameter ratio ($L/D \leq 4$) [3] are primarily governed by cross-section strength, with failure occurring when both steel and concrete reach their respective strength limits. Initially, under load, steel and concrete deform longitudinally, with steel exhibiting greater lateral expansion due to its higher Poisson's ratio compared to concrete. As load increases, the concrete core microcracks and expands faster than steel, leading to confinement by the steel tube and increased concrete strength. The level of confinement depends on the sectional shape and the diameter-to-thickness ratio, with circular sections enhancing concrete core strength. Thick-walled tubes effectively confine concrete, reaching steel yielding limits before failure due to concrete cracking. In thin-walled sections, failure may occur through elastic or inelastic local buckling of steel or shear failure in concrete, followed by steel tube buckling. Nonetheless, the concrete core delays and prevents local steel tube failure,

facilitating full development of yield stress before buckling. Additionally, infill concrete prevents inward buckling of the steel tube, reducing local strain concentration.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DATABASE

The literature contains numerous experimental and numerical studies on circular slender CFST columns. These studies have demonstrated the superior performance of these composite columns and have informed the development of current standard design codes. Several experimental databases, such as those developed by Goode [4], Aho and Leon [5], Denavit and Hajjar [6], Gourley [7], Kim [8], and Perea [9], have been utilized. However, a detailed comparison of these databases with the original reports has revealed some errors, particularly in the consideration of cylindrical compressive strength when the concrete strength was measured in cubic tests. In this paper, the authors have updated these databases, including new tests, and corrected the identified errors. All the references are included in Table 1, as well the measured geometrical and mechanical values of the different test.

This paper considers a total of 670 experimental tests on circular slender columns, including tests with high-strength materials and thin-walled sections (diameter of the cross-section and thickness of the steel tube). Figure 1 illustrates the type of loading application, where the steel tube and the concrete core are loaded simultaneously. A summary review is compiled in Table 1 and Table 2, while Figures 2 and 3 contain the experimental data information.

Fig. 1. Type of load application and stub column geometry

Table 1. Experimental database test of CFT stub columns from literature. Measure values.

Reference	N° test	D/t	L/D	f_y (MPa)	f_c (MPa)
Chapman & Neogi (1966) [5]	4	14.47 - 28.47	2.89 - 2.89	270 - 302	32.6 - 33.2
Gardner (1968) [5]	11	33.76 - 64.61	1.8 - 1.81	200.2 - 338.1	18.2 - 37.1
Zhong (new) (1978) [5]	9	23.6 - 24	2.22 - 3.7	271.9 - 409.64	28.6 - 30.7
Tang et al (1982) [4]	26	24 - 100	2 - 3.94	232.3 - 602.7	9.9 - 48.35
Cai et al (1984) [5]	20	27 - 45.71	0.81 - 3.97	249.9 - 338.88	26.56 - 46.57
Sakino (1985) [5]	6	17.85 - 192.3	1.96 - 2	244 - 320	18 - 37.4
Wang (1985) [4]	5	21.62 - 55.36	1.96 - 2.02	235 - 235	17.4 - 26.6
Cheng (1988) [4]	5	13.71 - 36.66	4 - 4	223 - 304	33.2 - 33.2
Goode (1989) [4]	4	22.02 - 31.62	3.02 - 3.12	226.7 - 226.7	30.2 - 48
Luksha (1991) [8]	10	31.36 - 105.8	3 - 3	291.4 - 381.5	15 - 46
Sakino (1991) [8]	12	19.77 - 58	2.01 - 2.06	249 - 283	22.1 - 45.7

Tsuji (1991) [8]	2	25.4 - 32.65	2 - 2	339 - 350	33.4 - 33.4
Kilpatrick (1994) [8]	9	34.54 - 42.37	3.5 - 3.5	380 - 390	57 - 57
O'Shea_Bridge (1994) [8]	6	165.21 - 165.21	3.45 - 3.49	330 - 330	94.7 - 110.3
Han (1995) [4]	1	55.65	3.04	354.6	60.75
Kato (1995) [5]	12	25 - 520.03	0.29 - 3	299.8 - 471.4	27.7 - 82.4
Matsui (1995) [5]	1	39.61	4	358.7	40.9
Han (1996) [4]	1	35.5	2.97	354.6	60.75
Bridge & O'Shea (1997) [8]	30	58.51 - 220.93	3.46 - 3.51	185.7 - 363.3	41 - 108
Han (1997) [4]	3	23.65 - 56.78	2.94 - 3.07	309.5 - 357.7	60.75 - 60.75
Lahlou_Lachemi (1999) [8]	8	13.63 - 35.9	2.97 - 3	344 - 457	56.6 - 120
Saisho (1999) [4]	29	33.86 - 58.98	3 - 3	341 - 462.6	25.4 - 135.6
Tan et al (1999) [4]	13	18.14 - 125	3.49 - 3.5	232 - 429	106.02 - 106.02
Zhong (Harbin) (1999) [4]	31	23.65 - 85.5	2.87 - 3.92	264.9 - 357.7	18.4 - 42.7
Han (2000) [4]	1	29.57	2.98	324.3	60.75
Yamamoto (2000) [8]	13	30.69 - 33.63	2.99 - 3.01	335 - 452	23.2 - 52.2
Han (2001) [4]	1	32.97	2.95	433	60.75
Kodur_Wang (2001) [8]	8	16.82 - 33.65	2.97 - 2.97	430.5 - 480	36.5 - 100
Han (2002) [8]	1	25.36	2.97	482.5	60.75
Yu et al. (2002) [4]	28	19.87 - 165	3.03 - 3.35	338 - 438	87.1 - 91.8
Bai & Li (2003) [4]	4	25.23 - 43.15	3.17 - 3.27	342 - 379	24.2 - 24.2
Han (2003) [8]	1	32.49	2.99	373.3	60.75
Han & Yao (2003) [8]	12	33.33 - 66.66	3 - 3	303.5 - 303.5	46.8 - 46.8
Uenaka et al (2003) [8]	3	73.69 - 176.33	2.83 - 2.85	221 - 308	18.7 - 18.7
Zhang (2003) [4]	36	24.46 - 50.42	2.96 - 3.03	325.3 - 392	35.7 - 61.7
Giakoumelis & Lam (2004) [3]	13	22.91 - 30.53	2.6 - 2.63	343 - 343	25.1 - 83.9
Han_Yao (2004) [5]	12	33.33 - 66.66	3 - 3	303.5 - 303.5	52.76 - 52.76
Sakino et al (2004) [5]	36	16.69 - 152.02	3 - 3	279 - 853	25.4 - 85.1
Tao, Han, Zhao (2004) [8]	2	60 - 60	3 - 3	275.9 - 275.9	40.56 - 40.56
Ellobody et al (2006) [8]	6	52.42 - 79.51	3 - 3	507 - 525	25.4 - 85.1
Beck et al. (2007) [10]	9	19.05 - 34.11	3 - 3	287.33 - 342.95	32.68 - 105.45
Gupta (2007) [11]	48	32.59 - 38.94	3.02 - 3.8	360 - 360	12.89 - 32.43
Yu, Ding, Cai (2007) [12]	6	45.81 - 60.66	2.96 - 3.09	350 - 350	38.51 - 78.74
Yu, Tao, Wu (2008) [13]	4	52.63 - 52.63	3 - 3	404 - 404	130.37 - 130.37
Oliveira et al. (2009) [14]	4	34.11 - 34.11	2.99 - 2.99	287.33 - 287.33	18.12 - 105.5
Uenaka, Kitoh, sonoda (2010) [15]	3	73.83 - 176.66	2.83 - 2.84	221 - 308	18.7 - 18.7
Xiong Riu et al. (2012) [16]	5	41.25 - 41.25	3 - 3	210 - 210	27.5 - 27.5
	670	13.64 - 220.93	0.30 - 4.00	185.70 - 853	9.90 - 135.60

Table 2. Experimental database test of CFT stub columns from literature. The sectional classification has been done with the EC4 criteria, and the strength resistance of concrete is measured in 150 x 300 mm probe test

N° tests	Compact section		Slender section	
	$f_c \leq 50$ MPa	$f_c > 50$ MPa	$f_c \leq 50$ MPa	$f_c > 50$ MPa
670	322	198	72	78

The limits imposed by EC4 are considered for the sectional classification, compact or slender, as well the consideration of high strength concrete.

Fig. 2. Classification of test according to the materials employed. Limits imposed by Eurocode 4.

Fig. 3. Classification of test according to the materials employed and the sectional slenderness.

3 EUROPEAN CODE

The EC4 proposes two different models depending on the cross-sectional shape: rectangular/square or circular. In the case of circular section, for concentric axial load and relative slenderness under 0.50, the model considers enhancing the concrete contribution and reducing the steel capacity.

$$N_{EC4,CCFT} = \eta_a \cdot A_a \cdot f_y + \left(1 + \eta_c \cdot \frac{t}{D} \cdot \frac{f_y}{f_c}\right) A_c \cdot f_c \quad (1)$$

$$\eta_a = 0.25 \cdot (3 + 2 \cdot \bar{\lambda}) \leq 1.0 \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_c = 4.9 - 18.5 \cdot \bar{\lambda} + 17 \cdot \bar{\lambda}^2 \geq 0.00 \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{N_{pLRk}}{N_{cr}}} \quad (4)$$

$$N_{pLRk} = A_a \cdot f_y + A_c \cdot f_c \quad (5)$$

$$N_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 \cdot (EI)_{eff}}{L^2} \quad (6)$$

$$(EI)_{eff} = E_a \cdot I_a + 0.60 \cdot E_{cm} \cdot I_c \quad (7)$$

Where η_c is the coefficient of confinement for the concrete, η_a is the coefficient for the steel tube, is the relative slenderness of the column, N_{cr} is the critical axial load and EI_{eff} the effective flexural stiffness for calculation of relative slenderness.

The model is valid in the ranges summarized in table 3.

Table 3. Limits imposed by the Eurocode 4: materials and sectional aspect.

	Steel	Concrete	Local buckling
EC4:2004	$235 \leq f_y \leq 460$ (MPa) $E_a = 210.000$ MPa	$25 \leq f_c \leq 50$ (MPa) $E_c = 22000 \cdot \left(\frac{f_c}{10}\right)^{0.3}$	$\frac{D}{t} \leq 90 \cdot \varepsilon^2$ $\varepsilon = \sqrt{\frac{235}{f_y}}$

4 EXPERIMENTAL TEST VERSUS EUROCODE

In order to compare the current model, a comparative study of predictions of experimental data has been done. It has been represented the error in predicting, materialized as the ratio of ultimate experimental load measure, and predicting load for EC4.

Experimental data versus results have been classified attending to materials employed and sectional slenderness.

In figure 4, the error is represented and also a line in the unit and two dash lines in 0.9 and 1.1. These values help to evaluate the accuracy of the model. All the points below the line 1 are unsafe.

Fig. 4. Classification of test according to the materials employed and the sectional slenderness.

In Table 4, the statistical analysis of the error is represented, and the classification is following the materials employed and the sectional slenderness.

Table 4. Analysis of the experimental results and the European code.

Compact section $(D/t) \leq 90 \cdot \epsilon^2$						Slender section $(D/t) > 90 \cdot \epsilon^2$					
$f_c \leq 50 \text{ MPa}$			$f_c > 50 \text{ MPa}$			$f_c \leq 50 \text{ MPa}$			$f_c > 50 \text{ MPa}$		
Mean	Desv.	Unsafe	Mean	Desv.	Unsafe	Mean	Desv.	Unsafe	Mean	Desv.	Unsafe
1.08	5.83	33.33%	0.99	1.13	55.20%	0.99	1.09	55.36%	0.95	0.54	71.43%

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper an extensive experimental database on CFT stub columns has been compiled. It includes tests with normal and high strength materials and different sectional aspects ratio (ratio between large dimension and thickness) which it is a measure of the susceptibility of the steel tube to suffer local buckling. The applicability of actual current design EC4 has been evaluated using the available experimental data. From the investigation of the present study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The Eurocode is safe for normal strength materials and compact sections.

- The accuracy of the models decreases specially for slender sections, where the steel tube trends to suffer local buckling. This phenomenon is even worse when the strength of the concrete increases.
- Despite the model is unsafe for slender sections and high strength concrete, the standard deviation is reduced, so it looks possible to present a little correction to include more options in the Eurocode in order to consider high strength materials and slender sections.

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